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WV INTERNATIONAL CONGRESS

V ENGINEERING, ENVIRONMENT AND MATERIALS IN PROCESS INDUSTRY EEM2023

BOOK OF ABSTRACTS

JAHORINA
MARCH 20-23, 2023

REPUBLIC OF SRPSKA
BOSNIA AND HERZEGOVINA

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UNAUTHORISED SUBSTANCES IN FOOD SUPPLEMENTS - PHOSPHODIESTERASE-5 INHIBITORS

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Abstract

Considering high prevalence of use of food supplements, especially their expansion in the last decade due to easy access on the internet, a serious associated safety issues associated have been raised. In order to meet the expectation of their customers, some producers have turned to the illicit and dangerous practice of product adulteration with unauthorized synthetic adulterants. Food technologies should be a key in meeting the dual challenge of enhancing both the quality and safety of food supplements. The Rapid Alert System for Food and Feed (RASFF) was established in order to speed up the flow of information in order to enable a quick reaction when risks to public health are discovered in the food chain. RASFF provides a tremendous database of countless food hazards. The aim of this paper was to search the RASFF database (criteria: food category "dietetic food, food supplements, fortified food", hazard category "composition") for the 2011-2022 period, in order to detect food supplements adulterated with unauthorized substances from the group of phosphodiesterase-5 inhibitors (PDE-5). The RASFF database was examined electronically and manually, and all occurrences of PDE-5 inhibitors and their synthetic derivatives were individually verified and counted. The records showed more than a hundred notifications, and their distribution by year was fairly even with the maximum of 33 notifications in 2019. But if we look at notifications related to PDE-5 inhibitors in relation to the total number of notifications for food supplements in a given year, then in 2022 we have a sharp peak where almost 40% of notifications refer to PDE-5 inhibitors. In a total of 179 notifications related to food supplements adulterated with PDE-5 inhibitors, 235 occurrences of PDE-5 inhibitors and their analogues were recorded, as a substantial number of supplements showed simultaneous presence of several unauthorized PDE-5 inhibitors and/or their analogues. The most frequent were those of the sildenafil group (66%), followed by the tadalafil group (28%), vardenafil (5%) and finally avanafil with only one notification. Although sildenafil and tadalafil were most frequently detected, their analogues and synthetic derivatives were also found in 61 cases, and the numbers continued to increase over the years due to producers' attempts to avoid adulterant detection by existing analytical methods.

A multidisciplinary approach that includes scientists in food technology, nutrition and public health is essential to our ability to respond to the global problem of the illegal practice of using unauthorized substances in food supplements.

Key words: PDE-5 inhibitors, analogues, food supplements, adulterants.